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Dinesh Kalla, Fnu Samaah

Microsoft Technical Support Engineer Charlotte NC USA

kalladinesh@outlook.com

US Bank Team Lead Chicago IL, USA

Fsamaah@alumni.harrisburgu.edu

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ABSTRACT

Network security and information system protection from intrusions is a top priority, and intrusion detection systems play a crucial part in this effort. This paper explores an employ of AI and data-driven techniques for enhancing anomaly detection in cloud security, utilizing the CIS-CICIDS2017 dataset. The study develops a DL-CNN model aimed at accurately detecting irregular network traffic patterns and identifying various threats, including DDoS, Heartbleed, and other attacks. Among the models evaluated, the CNN model achieved the best performance, with an accuracy97%, precision93%, recall92%, and an F1-score93%. The CNN outperforms more conventional ML models like RF and GNB, as shown by these data. A finding highlight an effectiveness of AI-driven approaches in strengthening cloud security and provide insights for future research to further improve anomaly detection in dynamic cloud environments.

KEYWORDS: Data-Driven Techniques, Anomaly Detection, Cloud Security, SMOTE**1. INTRODUCTION**

Cloud computing's explosive growth across sectors has fundamentally changed how businesses handle, store, and analyse data. With this increasing reliance on cloud services, security concerns have become more pronounced, particularly in the area of anomaly detection[1]. Anomalies in cloud environments, whether caused by system faults or malicious activities[2], pose serious threats to the integrity and availability of cloud services. As a result, effective anomaly detection systems ae essential to ensuring the security of cloud infrastructures. In recent years[3][4], Artificial Intelligence (AI) and data-driven techniques have emerged as powerful tools in developing sophisticated anomaly detection frameworks that can identify potential threats in real-time[5][6][7]. AI-based techniques leverage machine learning algorithms, deep learning models, and data-driven approaches to detect anomalous patterns in large-scale cloud environments. These models are trained using historical data to distinguish between typical and anomalous cloud network behaviour [8][9]. Additionally, AI systems can continuously learn from new data, enabling them to adapt to evolving threats in dynamic cloud infrastructures[10][11].

Recent studies have explored various AI and ML algorithms for anomaly detection in cloud environments, including unsupervised learning methods[12][7], neural networks, and hybrid approaches that combine multiple models to improve detection accuracy[13][14]. Methods such as LSTM networks, RF, and SVMs have shown encouraging outcomes in detecting known and new abnormalities. Companies may reduce the likelihood of serious security breaches by combining these methods with cloud monitoring technologies [15][16].

This study's objective is to create and assess advanced artificial intelligence (AI) and data-driven models for enhancing anomaly detection in cloud security using the CSE-CICIDS2017 dataset. By leveraging machine learning techniques, the research aims to accurately identify irregular network traffic patterns, distinguishing between benign and malicious activities. The study focuses on improving detection efficiency through data preprocessing, feature importance analysis, and model optimization using a DL-CNN. This work seeks to provide more reliable methods for detecting threats such as DDoS and other attacks, ultimately contributing to the improvement of cloud infrastructure security. The study's primary contributions are as follows:

- The study develops advanced AI and ML models to accurately detect irregular patterns and threats in cloud networks.
- The research employs a widely recognized cybersecurity dataset, incorporating both normal and malicious network traffic, for comprehensive model training and evaluation.
- The study applies data preprocessing techniques, including SMOTE for addressing class imbalances, to enhance model performance and data quality.
- Key features influencing anomaly detection, such as flow duration and bandwidth, are identified and analyzed to improve model accuracy.
- A DL-CNN is implemented with optimized hyperparameters to classify network traffic, demonstrating high accuracy in detecting anomalies.

Structure of paper

This document is formatted as follows: The literature on ML algorithms for identifying abnormalities in cloud security is reviewed in Section II. Section III describes the models, preparation methods, and CSE-CICIDS2017 dataset. Section IV offers an outcome of an evaluation and comparative analysis of the models. Key results and suggestions for more study are presented in Section V's conclusion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews the existing research on ML and DL models used for anomaly detection in cloud security. In this paper, Chkirbene, Erbad and Hamila, 2019, propose the EIDC system, a cutting-edge firewall design for a secure cloud computing environment. EIDC employs a revolutionary combination technique called most frequent decision, using 11 nodes, to detect and classify the incoming traffic packets. They use the publicly accessible UNSW-NB-15 dataset to produce our findings. The findings indicate that, in comparison to complicated trees, EICD increases anomaly detection by 24% [2],

In this paper, Salman et al., 2017, examine both detecting and classifying anomalies, as opposed to only locating them, as is common in contemporary research. Results show greater than 99% detection accuracy and 93.6% categorisation accuracy, with some assaults unable to be classified. Furthermore, we contend that similar categorisation may be used to multi-cloud systems using the same ML methodologies [16],

This paper, Cui and He, 2016, introduces a paradigm that blends cloud computing and ML. MapReduce is used to process the traffic data once it has been stored in HDFS. Moreover, accuracy and efficiency are confirmed using NB and SVM. Lastly, with an accuracy of over 90%, the testing results demonstrate that this method works effectively for detection [17], .

In this work, Aboueata et al., 2019, examine the efficacy of two popular ML approaches, ANN and SVM, in identifying anomalous activity or intrusions in cloud environments. They have examined the performance of ANN and SVM strategies in the development of ML models. To train and evaluate the models, we utilised the UNSW-NB-15 dataset. They find that when given the right characteristics, SVM and ANN approaches can identify anomalies with an accuracy of 91% and 92%, respectively [18], .

This paper, Zhang et al., 2015, offers a method for detecting anomalies that incorporates both a classifier and a transformation model. Each element is converted into a vector by the converting model, and the values inside the vector are acquired by feature training using NB and statistical techniques. This allows for query-free analysis of URIs or URLs in online logs and the establishment of a common normal standard for numerous websites. An experimental findings demonstrate that our method can achieve a false alarm rate of less than 1.5% and a detection rate of above 98% [19], .

Table 1 shows prior studies on anomaly detection in cloud security using machine and deep learning methods, comparing their effectiveness.

TABLE 1: SUMMARY OF RELATED WORK ON ANOMALY DETECTION USING ML AND DL TECHNIQUES.

Author	Dataset	Methodology	Performance	Limitation/Contribution
[2]	UNSW-NB15	Most Frequent Decision combining past nodes' decisions with current ML decision	Improved anomaly detection by 24% compared to complex tree	Increases learning performance and accuracy by combining past decisions
[16]	Public dataset	LR and RF for detection and categorization	99% detection accuracy, 93.6% categorization accuracy	The similarity of attacks makes categorisation less accurate.
[17]	HDFS Traffic Data	Hadoop with HDFS for storage, MapReduce for processing, Weka for algorithm selection	Detection accuracy above 90%	Good detection performance using a big data framework
[18]	UNSW-NB15	ANN and SVM with feature engineering and parameter tuning	91% for SVM, 92% for ANN	Higher accuracy achieved with reduced feature set
[19]	50.1GB Web Logs	Transforming model converting entry to vector, Naive Bayes for classification	Detection rate > 98%, false alarm rate < 1.5%	Unified anomaly detection for different websites with low false alarm rate

A. Research Gap

The review of current intrusion detection and classification systems highlights key gaps in research. While detection accuracy has improved, categorizing similar types of attacks remains challenging, with categorization performance often lagging behind. Many approaches rely on complex models that increase computational overhead, limiting scalability in real-time environments. Additionally, big data frameworks enhance detection but lack agility in adapting to evolving threats in multi-cloud settings. These gaps suggest a need for future research to improve categorization accuracy, reduce complexity, and enhance adaptability in dynamic, real-time environments.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The aim of this research is to explore AI and data-driven techniques to enhance anomaly detection in cloud security. It focuses on developing advanced models to accurately identify irregular patterns and threats in cloud networks, improving the efficiency and security of cloud infrastructures. The evaluation's findings will contribute to the improvement of the methodology's prediction for anomaly detection using the CIS-CICIDS2017 dataset, which contains labeled network traffic data, including both benign and malicious activities, for developing an anomaly detection model. Data preprocessing is crucial for handling inconsistencies and improving data quality before applying machine learning techniques. SMOTE is used for data balancing to address class imbalances. Feature importance is assessed to identify key features influencing attack detection, such as flow duration and bandwidth. The dataset is divided into 70% training and 30% testing sets. A DL-CNN model is implemented, with layers including pooling, convolutional, and fully connected layers, and the model is trained using hyperparameters like a learning rate of 0.0001, batch size of 64, and the Adam optimizer. The CNN model classifies network traffic based on features, with high performance demonstrated by its training and validation accuracy. The Figure 1 flowchart illustrates the several procedures and phases that make up the study design process.

Figure 1 ML model flowchart for anomaly detection.

The detailed explanations of each step in a data flow diagram are provided below.

A. Dataset Description with visualization

The University of New Brunswick's CIC created the CIS-CICIDS2017 dataset, which is extensively utilised in the area of cybersecurity for network analysis and intrusion detection studies. It includes a variety of network traffic samples, both malicious and benign, which enable academics and practitioners to create and assess IDSs and algorithms. It contains tagged data for several attack types and covers a broad variety of network attack situations. Collected over seven days, it includes both normal network traffic and simulated intrusions, encompassing 225,745 packages with over 80 features. The dataset simulates a variety of attacks, including Heartbleed, Brute Force, DDoS, Web, Botnet, DoS, and Infiltration attacks. DDoS attacks are characterized by attributes like flow duration, bandwidth, and packet intervals, with larger values often correlating with DDoS activity. The dataset provides a valuable resource for evaluating intrusion detection systems (IDS) by offering a realistic representation of both normal and malicious traffic.

Figure 2: The frequency count of each attack type.

Figure 2 shows a distribution of different types of attacks in a dataset analyzed by the CNN. The 'Benign' category dominates, suggesting most network events are normal, whereas various attack types like FTP-Patator, SSH-Patator, DoS Hulk, and others show significantly fewer occurrences.

Figure 3: Feature Importance

Figure 3 represents, bar plot that ranks the importance of different features used by the model to predict the attack types. The feature 'Time' appears to be the most important, followed by 'Flow Bytes/s' and 'Flow Packets/s', which might indicate that temporal and flow characteristics are critical in identifying the nature of network traffic and potential attacks.

B. Prediction DL model for Anomaly detection (Convolutional Neural Network):

The most used picture algorithms are CNNs. CNNs are often used in object identification, image classification, and image recognition, among other applications. The most common use of CNNs in DL is the categorisation of images. Furthermore, CNN is a dataset for high-dimensional images; often, a single image would include thousands of pixels representing complicated, high-volume features. CNNs are models powered by multilayer perceptrons. Three distinct layers are used by CNNs: convolutional, pooling, and fully connected. The connections between these layers and neural networks are stronger. A separate purpose is served by each layer. A convolutional layer has been utilised to extract features. The extracted function is used by a fully connected-layer to identify a category of a current item. The purpose of a pooling layer is to minimise the number of network parameters and feature mappings.

Convolutional Layer: A local connection idea and the weight distribution theory are used to construct feature maps using convolutional layers. Utilising the benefits of the highly linked local pixel neighbourhood and location-independent local picture statistics, we are able to decrease the number of parameters by utilising local connectivity and weight distribution goals. We have attached the weight distribution model for your review. Previously, a set of weights known as a "filter bank" ensured that each unit (neurone) in a feature map had a "local link" to its immediate neighbourhood. In a feature map, every unit shares a filter row. Additionally, many feature maps use distinct filter banks. The activation function takes the weighted sum of each unit and transforms it using a nonlinear algorithm. Each subsequent unit is weighted and added to the activation function, which is a nonlinear transformation function.

The layer's fundamental parameters are Kernel Size, Depth, Stride, and Padding. Each has a certain task, which is as follows:

- **Kernel Size:** The convolution filter's spatial size.
- **Depth:** A depth of a filter is represented by a third dimension of the filter.
- **Stride:** The amount by which the convolution filter moves over a certain area of the input data is indicated by the stride parameter.
- **Padding:** Determines the range and quantity of edges that should be zero-padded from the input.

Pooling layer: The input's spatial dimension is decreased by the pooling layer. Applying this to a whole input, one depth slice at a time, is possible using a sliding window. To find the maximum or average value of a geographic place, CNNs use pooling processes. While u and v represent the geographic position of the input slice k , $f(u, v, k)$ is utilised to get a local patch by a previous-layer, and α and β represent the dimensions of a spatial window utilised for a pooling process, equation (1) illustrates the procedure for both. In equations 1 and 2, a pooled_pixel at slice k is represented by $f_{avg}(k)$ and $f_{max}(k)$.

$$\hat{f}_{avg}(k) = 1/\alpha \times \beta \times \sum f(u: u + \alpha, v: v + \beta, k) \dots (1)$$

$$f_{max}(k) = MAX(f(u: u + \alpha, v: v + \beta, k)) \dots (2)$$

Fully connected layer: All of the neurones in a fully connected_layer, a particular kind of convolutional_layer, have been shrunk to a 1 x 1 spatial dimension. All of them are connected by the depth of the data.

$$y_j = f(\sum z_i \cdot w_{i,j} + b_j \quad m \quad i = 1) \dots (3)$$

Where y_j is the neurone that produces an output after applying the function $f(z)$ to the input z_i from the layer before it, the fully connected layer, shown in Equation (3), uses an input data and filter-weights to compute the dot product among every neurone. The function uses the dot product of every individual weight j of the fully linked_layer plus the bias b_j to get the total of all inputs z_i [26][27][28].

These hyperparameters were used to create the CNN training model:

The suggested CNN model was put into practice using the following hyperparameters: 192 hidden nodes, 64 batch size, learning rate = 0.0001, categorical cross-entropy loss, activation function = "SoftMax," and the "Adam" optimiser. In sum, the parameters that could be trained and those that could not were 30,214', 29,830', and 384', respectively. As a result, the CNN model took 20.66 minutes to train and 0.21 seconds to be tested. The resulting validation accuracy, loss, training accuracy, and training loss were all as follows.

C. Evaluation of parameter

F1-score, recall, accuracy, and precision are some of the assessment criteria used to evaluate anomaly detection algorithms. A model's performance may be evaluated using a number of metrics, such as recall, accuracy, precision, and F1-score, which combines two of these aspects.

1) Confusion Matrix

This confusion matrix may be used as a tool that can evaluate the classifier's performance in recognising tuples from distinct classes [20][21]. The classifier's True-Positive and True-Negative values indicate when it correctly classified the data, while the False-Positive and False-Negative values indicate when it misclassified the data[22][23][24][25].

- **TP (True Positive):** The amount of data that is valuable both in terms of its accuracy and its potential use.
- **FP (False Positive):** A quantity of information including both positive and negative forecasted value.
- **FN (False Negative):** A large quantity of data having a positive predicted value and a negative actual value.
- **TN (True Negative):** A quantity of information having both a negative predicted value and a negative actual value.

A dataset's performance may be evaluated using the following metrics:[29-35]

1) Accuracy

Accuracy, which measures the proportion of actual observations to predicted ones, is one of the most intuitive measures of performance. The following mathematical expression can be found in equation (4):

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \dots (4)$$

2) Precision

Precision may be defined as the degree to which actual observations match theoretical predictions. The corresponding equation (5) is shown below:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{(TP + FP)} \dots (5)$$

3) Recall

A number of incursions identified by a system, rather than a number of actual invasions, may be used to determine recall. The equation (6) is shown below.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \dots (6)$$

4) F1-Score

The F1 Score is calculated by averaging the precision and recall numbers. Both positive and negative values are accepted by this value. The corresponding equation (7) is shown below:

$$F1Score = 2 * \frac{precision * recall}{precision + recall} \dots (7)$$

The following criteria are used to determine an algorithm's evaluation parameters, which include f1-score, recall, accuracy, and precision. [35-45]

4. EXPERIMENT RESULT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section provides the performance outcomes of various anomaly detection models applied within cloud security contexts. The efficiency of a proposed CNN model is displayed in Table 2, which compares it to other models employing the CIS-CICIDS2017 dataset. It evaluates the models based on F1-score, recall, accuracy, and precision, highlighting the superior performance of the CNN model in these metrics.

TABLE 2: CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK MODEL PERFORMANCE ON CIS-CICIDS2017 DATASET.

Parameter	CNN
Accuracy	0.97
Precision	0.93
Recall	0.92
F1-score	0.93

Figure Figure 4: The CNN model accuracy plot.

Figure 4 displayed an accuracy plots of a CNN across epochs. An accuracy (blue line) starts high and remains relatively stable throughout, achieving near-perfect performance. In contrast, the testing accuracy (red line) is much more volatile and generally lower, suggesting the model might be overfitting the training data.

Figure 5: The CNN model loss plot.

Figure 5 displays the loss values of the CNN model. A rapid drop and subsequent stabilisation of the loss (blue line) at a low value suggests that a model is effectively learning from the training data. The testing loss (red line), however, shows higher variability and tends to increase slightly over time, which could be a sign of overfitting or instability in how the model generalizes to new, unseen data.

Figure 6: CNN model derived confusion matrix.

In Figure 6, we can see the confusion matrix, which represents a classification performance of a CNN model. It shows a true classes vs. a predicted classes, with high values along the diagonal (indicating correct predictions). Most classes show strong diagonal values, suggesting good classification performance, but there are non-zero values off-diagonal, indicating some misclassifications.

A. Comparative Analysis

This section compares machine learning models—GNB, RF, DT, AD, and CNN—using the CIS-CICIDS2017 dataset for anomaly detection in cloud security, focusing on F1-score, recall, accuracy, and precision.

TABLE 3: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS-BASED ON ANOMALY DETECTION IN CLOUD SECURITY.

Models	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
GNB[22]	55.4	0.66	0.55	0.58
RF[23]	0.86	0.99	0.86	0.50
AD[24]	0.81	0.85	0.94	0.89
CNN	0.97	0.93	0.92	0.93

According to Table 3, which shows the results of this comparison of ML models for anomaly detection in cloud security using the CIS-CICIDS2017 dataset, the CNN model performs better than all of the others with a 97% accuracy, 93% precision, 92% recall, and 93% F1-score. The Random Forest (RF) model shows strong precision at 99% but falls short according to recall(86%) and F1-score(50%), highlighting a potential imbalance in its predictions. The AdaBoost model performs reasonably well with a recall94% and an F1-score89%, but its overall accuracy (81%) is lower compared to CNN. In contrast, the Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB) model exhibits the weakest performance, with an accuracy55.4%, precision66%, recall55%, and an F1-score58%. Overall, the CNN model clearly outperforms the others, making it the most reliable choice for anomaly detection in cloud security.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Network anomalies might be defined as potential dangers that have occurred or not occurred in the past. Despite much research, securing networks from hostile access remains a formidable challenge. In conclusion, this study successfully demonstrates the effectiveness of AI and data-driven techniques, particularly the CNN, for anomaly detection in cloud security employing the CIS-CICIDS2017 dataset. The CNN model outperformed traditional machine learning models with 97% accuracy. These findings support the idea that models powered by AI may greatly improve the identification of suspicious network traffic and other security risks, which in turn helps to strengthen the safety of cloud infrastructure.

For future work, research could focus on further optimizing the CNN model to enhance its generalization capabilities and reduce overfitting. Additionally, integrating hybrid models that combine CNNs with other advanced machine learning algorithms, such as LSTMs or attention mechanisms, could improve anomaly detection in more complex cloud environments. Expanding the dataset to include more recent and varied attack types could also ensure that the model remains robust against evolving cyber threats.

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